

Nietzsche on Mask and Authenticity

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Nietzsche's conception of the mask is a key feature of his view on authenticity. In some of his works, he seems to argue that when the mask obscures the self, the latter one almost disappears under the guise of its cover. This is a position that Jung will later call identification with persona. The mask of the soul "can grow into our flesh" (Hannah 2000, 77) and in this circumstance it is almost impossible to discern between persona and ego. In this perspective, the mask is merely a negative factor. "Are you for real? Or only an actor? A representative? Or the represented?—In the end, you are really only an imitation of an actor..." (Nietzsche 2006, 'Arrows and Epigrams', §38). In the original text, Nietzsche is even more explicit, literally asking: *Bist du echt?* ("Are you authentic?") Authenticity and acting are diametrically opposed in this particular aphorism. Moreover, one is asked: "are you ... a representative [*ein Vertreter*] or the represented [*das Vertretene selbst*]?"

In a posthumous fragment from 1887, Nietzsche is targeting the same issue, inquiring "whether one is *genuine* or merely an *actor*; whether, as actor, one is genuine or merely a counterfeit actor; whether one is a 'representative' or that which is represented itself—whether a 'person' or merely a rendezvous of persons..." (KSA, Vol. 12, pp. 537-8, 10[145], Fall 1887). What does it mean to either represent or to be the represented? Perhaps we are reminded of the contrast between the self-referentiality of autonomous identity ("I represent and I speak for myself") and to the inability of assuming personhood ("I haven't found my voice yet, I represent other ideas and people"). The 'tip' of the 'arrow' is even sharper: "In the end, you are really only an imitation of an actor." If the 'actor' is inauthentic, its imitation – the mask of a mask – is doubly inauthentic. Patricia Dixon is certain right in referring to an authentic "labyrinth of masks behind masks" (Dixon 1999, 211), which obstructs the person behind them. In the fragment from 1887, Nietzsche alludes between the dichotomy between the mask and the mask of the mask, pointing out to a secondary level of inauthenticity: one can be a genuine actor or "merely a counterfeit actor", in other words one can be a good copy or a bad 'copy of a copy'. He furthermore asks whether he is "a 'person' or merely a rendezvous of persons". Am I=I,

emulating the divine pattern, or am I= $I_1 + I_2 + \dots + I_x$, a nearly infinite collection of subpersonalities? Am I moving toward becoming the Self, or toward the perfect Mask?

In a related fragment from 1888, Nietzsche compares the modern artist to a hysteric, who excels in the art of dissimulation [*Verstellung*], lying “for the sheer pleasure of lying”. He also calls him “false” [*falsch*], noting that “he is no longer a person, at most a rendezvous of persons” (KSA, Vol. 13, pp. 517-8, 16[89], Summer 1888). In a pre-Jungian manner, Nietzsche emphasizes the distance between the self and the “mask of the soul,” persona stifling the person. We have here the same differentiation between *falsch* and *echt* like in the ‘arrow’ from *The Twilight of Idols*, between falsity and authenticity. In another fragment from 1880, Nietzsche refers to the internal disjunction of inauthenticity, to the disharmony of bad faith: “But your faith must be so blind, so immense and fantastic, to overcome the suffering of the guilty conscience... Oh, actors to yourself!” (KSA, Vol. 9, p. 182, 5[8], Summer 1880). If I lie as an actor to myself, I live a fake existential project and I risk never finding my own voice and meaning. Just as Nietzsche likens the modern artist to a hysteric, he sets the great moralist against the figure of the actor—whose peril lies in identifying too fully with his role, in allowing dissimulation [*Verstellung*] to imperceptibly harden into nature. Here, the hierarchy of good and evil is overturned: the moralist must perform everything “under the guise of good,” modelling himself on none other than God—the “greatest immoralist in action”—who nonetheless persists in the pretense of goodness (KSA, Vol. 13, pp. 24–7, 11[54], November 1887–March 1888). Both God and the moralist thus enact a classical strategic axiom: if you are evil, wear the mask of the good.

But are lying and acting necessarily wrong? Turning now to Nietzsche’s second perspective on masks and authenticity, he observes that there “is a hatred of lying and disguise [*Verstellung*] that comes from a delicate sense of honour; there is also a hatred that comes from cowardice, since lying is forbidden by divine commandment. Too cowardly to lie...” (Nietzsche 2006, ‘Arrows and Epigrams’, §32). In this context, Nietzsche does not treat lying as an existential fault, but rather as an antitheological gesture of liberation. Siegfried Mandel points out that “intellectually and emotionally”, Nietzsche “lived a double life” and practiced *Verstellung* [‘dissimulation’], “an ironic adoption of masks, much as an actor uses them on stage and enjoys the artistic deception” (Mandel 2001, xviii). Thus, there is no surprise that Nietzsche is ambivalent about his former theory of authenticity. His fragment *The Actor* from 1884 is a testimony of his ambivalence: “It is a kind of *actor’s* art, the ability to temporarily assume a

foreign soul ... At the same time, a sign of *weakness* and lack of *unity* [Einheit]" (KSA, Vol. 11, p. 254, 26[393], Summer-Fall 1884, emphasis in the original). In the latter part of the fragment, we find the familiar accusation of the actor conceived as "a rendezvous of persons", a collection of masks that steal his soul. However, persona is not only inhibitive, but also expressive: the actor positively assumes "a foreign soul". Nietzsche anticipates here Thayer Greene's conception of the persona as an amplification of the actor's character. The purpose of the mask is "to reveal, not to conceal" (Greene 1975, 26).

Nietzsche's tactic here appears to be: if you are profound, pretend to be shallow (in its moral variant: "if you're good, pretend to be evil"). "Human beings who think deeply appear in their relations with others like actors because they must, in order to be understood, always first feign having a surface" (Nietzsche 2013, §232). The operative principle of this counter-authentic authenticity is encapsulated in the maxim "All that is profound loves a mask" (Nietzsche 2014, §40). We are often least authentic at the very moment we think we have touched authenticity—for the latter remains a fugitive ideal. Nietzsche recognized this treacherous dynamic and inverted it. One must feign truthfulness in lying, must search for the most eloquent mask. If most of us miss both authenticity and truth precisely through our earnest pursuit of them, Nietzsche suggests instead that the liar, the actor, *der Scheinende*—the one who only appears—embodies authenticity more profoundly, though in a negative and oblique way. This is Nietzsche's left-hand path to authenticity understood as 'divine' lie. "This belief in truth carries us, within ourselves, to its ultimate consequence—you know what it is: namely, that if there is anything at all worthy of adoration, it is appearance that must be adored, that the lie—and *not* the truth—is divine...?" (KSA, Vol. 12, pp. 242-3, 6[25], Summer 1886-Early 1887). Since most truths harden into lies, one must veil truth beneath a lie. The truth concealed in a lie is superior to a lying truth.

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